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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Anti Acne Facewash

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ABSTRACT

This study aim to design, formulate, and evaluate a medicated facewash for acne treatment, assessing its efficacy, safety, and stability. Ocimum gratissimum (OG) Linn belongs to the family Lamiaceae and found mostly in the savannah and coastal areas of different countries. Ocimum gratissimum is medicinal potential for acne vulgaris. We examine the phytochemistry of this herb, emphasizing its potent component like linolenic acid. These compounds have antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities that make them useful in the treatment of acne. Finally, clinical studies examining the safety and effectiveness of topical formulations derived from Ocimum gratissimum is reviewed, emphasizing their potential as monotherapies or adjuncts to conventional treatments. In summary, Ocimum gratissimum represent promising candidate for the development of novel, effective, and safe herbal therapy for acne vulgaris, offering a natural alternative for people seeking sustainable and holistic approaches to skincare.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics

Cosmetics means any article intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled, sprayed, or sprayed on or introduced into, or otherwise applied to, the human body or any part there for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness, or altering the appearance.

Facewash

A face wash is a facial care solution used to clean the skin on the face of makeup, dead skin

cells, oil, grime, and other forms of pollutants.

This aids in pore cleaning and shields the skin from conditions like acne.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plant material

Leaves of Ocimum gratissimum was collected from Kasargod district, Kerala in the month of March 2024.

Authentication of plant material

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The plant material were identified and authenticated by Dr. Subrahmanya Prasad k, Assistant professor Department of Botany, Nehru arts and science college, Kanhangad, Kasargod, Kerala.

Preparation of plant extract

5gm of *Ocimum gratissimum* powder was prepared from dry *Ocimum gratissimum* leaves. Powder was prepared by using grinder machine. 50ml of water and 5gm of powder were macerated, and left to stand for 24 hrs. After that filter the above mixture and filter liquid used for Facewash preparation.

Phytochemical screening of extract of *ocimum gratissimum*

Test for carbohydrate, proteins, alkaloid, glycosides, saponins, amino acids, flavonoids,

phytosterols, tannins and phenols were carried out using dispersion of 1g of formulation in 20 ml of water.

Preparation of facewash containing extract

Carbopol 940 was first blended with distilled water, and then allowed to swell for a day. Then the liquid is stirred using a mechanical stirrer. Calculated quantities of sodium lauryl sulphate were added to distilled water and heated on a water bath. The solution was cooled after dissolution is completed. Calculated quantities of *Ocimum gratissimum* extract was transferred into a beaker and mixed with Carbopol gel base, triethanolamine was added drop by drop and mixed properly. Preservatives, fragrance were also added and final weight was made to 100g using distilled water.

Sl no	Ingredients	Quantity (w/w)			Function
		F1	F2	F3	
1	Ether extract of <i>ocimum gratissimum</i>	4ml	4ml	4ml	Prevent acne
2	Carbopol 940	1.5g	2g	2.5g	Suspending agent
3	Triethanolamine	2.5ml	2ml	1.5ml	Increase integrity of skin barrier
4	Propylene glycol	2ml	2ml	2.5ml	Maintain moisture
5	Sodium lauryl sulphate	1g	1g	1g	Surfactant
6	Propyl paraben	1g	1g	1g	Preservative
7	Methyl paraben	0.1g	0.1g	0.1g	Increase shelf life
8	Tulsi oil	QS	QS	QS	Fragrance
9	Distilled water	QS to 100g	QS to 100g	QS to 100g	Vehicle

Methods of evaluation

A. Physical evaluation

Physical parameters such as color and appearance were evaluated.

B. Determination of pH

The pH of Facewash formulation was determined by using digital pH meter. About 2.5 gm of the Facewash was accurately weighed and dispersed in 25 ml of distilled water and stored for two hours. The pH of dispersions was measured by using pH meter.

C. Determination of spreadability

Formulation 0.5 gm were placed within a circle of 1 cm diameter pre-marked on a glass plate over which a second glass plate was placed. A weight of 5 gm was placed on upper glass plate for 5 minutes.

$$S_i = d \times \pi / 4$$

S = Spreadability

d = diameter

D. Viscosity

The viscosity of the facewash was determined by using Brookfield viscometer at 10 rpm. About 50g of the Facewash was taken in a beaker and spindle

was dipped in it for about 5 minutes and then the reading was recorded.

E. Foamability

A small quantity of Facewash was added to water in a beaker. After recording the initial volume, the beaker was shaken ten times to record the final volume.

Screening for antimicrobial activity

The bacteria lactobacillus is prepared from curd. The curd is filtered and the broth is incubated at 25°C for 24hrs. A sabouraud dextrose agar (150 ml) is autoclaved and poured to the already autoclaved plate and cooled to room temperature and allowed to solidify. The culture was spread on the agar surface aseptically by using sterilized

cotton. A sabouraud dextrose agar (150 ml) is autoclaved and poured to the already autoclaved plate and cooled to room temperature and allowed to solidify. The culture was spread on the agar surface aseptically by using sterilized cotton. After 48 hours, the plates were observed for the presence of inhibition of bacterial growth and it was indicated in the form of a clear zone of inhibition around each well containing different samples. The size of the inhibitory zone was measured in 'mm'. The zone of inhibition obtained for the developed herbal anti-acne facewash was compared with the standard. Amoxicillin disc was used as a standard.

Result

Phytochemicals present in prepared facewash

SI No.	Compounds	Petroleum ether	Chloroform	Ethanol	Aqueous extract
1	Alkaloid	-	-	-	+
2	Carbohydrate	+	+	+	+
3	Anthraquinones	+	+	+	+
4	Glycosides	+	+	+	+
5	Phenol	-	-	-	-
6	Flavanoid	-	-	-	+
7	Aminoacid & proteins	-	-	-	-
8	Steroids	-	-	-	+
9	Saponins	-	-	-	-
10	Tannins	-	-	-	+
11	Terpenoids	+	+	+	+

(+) = Present , (-) = absent

Evaluation of facewash

Physical evaluation

SI NO.	Formulation	Observation		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Colour	Dark green	Dark green	Dark green
2	Appearance	Clear and transparent	Clear and transparent	Clear and transparent
3	Homogenity	Dark green	Clear and transparent	Presence of lumbs

Determination of pH

	F1	F2	F3
pH	7.1	5.2	4.9

Spreadability

	F1	F2	F3
Spreadability	3.07cm/sec	6.06cm/sec	2.54cm/sec

Viscosity

	F1	F2	F3
Viscosity	3409.3	5406.5	8405.5

Phytochemical Screening Of Facewash Formulation

SI NO.	Compounds	Presence
1	Alkaloid	+
2	Carbohydrate	+
3	Anthraquinones	+
4	Glycosides	+
5	Phenol	-
6	Flavanoid	+
7	Amino acid & proteins	-
8	Steroids	+
9	Saponins	-
10	Tannins	+
11	Terpenoids	+

Screening of antimicrobial activity

SI No.	Bacteria	Diameter of zone of inhibition (mm)	
		Amoxycillin	Facewash
1	E.coli	10	7

DISCUSSION

Three formulations F1, F2 and F3 were prepared and subjected to different evaluations. Physical parameters were observed, and all formulations were dark green in colour and clear and transparent. F1 and F2 were homogenous in nature and F3 was found to show presence of lumps. pH of the formulations was tested using digital pH meter and F2 was found to show optimum pH suitable for the facial skin with a value of 5.2. Spreadability was tested and F2 showed best value in the test. Spreadability was comparatively poor for F1 and F3. Viscosity was tested using Brookfield viscometer. F1 and F2 showed satisfactory flow properties and F3 had bit higher viscosity and poor pourability. From these parameters F2 was found to be best as an herbal face wash. Phytochemical tests were performed for F2, and it was showing the presence of

Carbohydrate, Anthraquinones, Glycosides, Flavonoids, Steroids, Tannins and Terpenoids, which helps to prevent or reduce acne. Antimicrobial study was performed by using agar well diffusion method. F2 showed a zone of inhibition of 7mm. Thus, the formulation F2 was found to show optimum properties of herbal face wash for acne. And its effectiveness may be improved by some optimization of the formulation.

CONCLUSION

The aim of study is to formulate the herbal facewash using leaf extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* for anti-acne activity. Physicochemical and phytochemical investigations of leaves of *Ocimum gratissimum* have been reported here in this thesis work. The preliminary phytochemical screening of plant shows that the ether extracts shows the presence of major constituents such as glycosides, saponins,

flavonoids, terpenoids may contribute to anti-inflammatory activity which is beneficial in the treatment of acne. Phytoconstituents present in plants were extracted by maceration. Facewash containing herbal extract were prepared and the revealed that Carbopol 940 as a polymer showed good compatibility for facewash formulation. From results revealed that the prepared facewash formulation is good in appearance, homogeneity, and easily spreadable. Higher the value of viscosity greater the consistency of prepared facewash. The in-vitro anti-acne evaluation was done by using agar well diffusion method and anti-bacterial activity was measured in terms of zone of inhibition. The formulation produced a better zone of inhibition of about 7mm against *Lactobacillus* bacteria which was near to the zone of inhibition produced by standard Amoxicillin disc (10mm). However, in the present work herbal formulations reported to have more significant advantages over synthetic formulations. Hence, we conclude that herbal facewash for acne is effective, safe and ease of manufacturing and in the economic point of view they are cheap when compared to chemical based facewash.

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REFERENCES

1. Manta Saxeena, Jyothi Saxeena, Rajeev Nema, Dharmendra Singh and Abhishek Gupta. Phytochemistry of medicinal plant. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 2013; 1(6): 168-182.
2. P.Garodia, H.Ichikawa, N.Malani, G.Sethi, and B.P.Aggarwal. From ancient medicine to modern medicine: Ayurvedic concepts of health and their role in inflammation and cancer. *J Soc Integr Oncol*. 2007;1(5):25-37.
3. Fabio Firenzuoli and Luigi Gori. Herbal medicine today. *Clinical and research issues evidence*. 2007;4(1):37-40.
4. Goyal M, Samsal D and Nagori BP. *Ayurveda and ancient science of healing*. First edition. Intech publishers. 2012;12-14.
5. Cardini F, Wade C, Regalia AL, Gui S, Li W, Raschetti R, Kronenberg F. Clinical research in traditional medicine: priorities and methods. *Compl Ther Med*. 2006; 14:282–287.
6. S.Bale, K.Harding and D. Leeper. An introduction to wounds. *Am. J. Surg*. 1999;5(1):5- 12
7. J.Li, J.Chen, and R.Kirsener. Pathophysiology of Acute Wound Healing, *Journal of Drugs and Medicine*. 2007;25(1):9-18.
8. Pandey S, Meshya N and Viral D. Herbs play an important Role in the Field of Cosmetics.

- International Journal of Pharm. Tech Research. 2010; 2:632-639.
9. Jain A, Basal E. Inhibition of Propionibacterium acnes-induced mediators of inflammation by Indian herbs. *Phytomedicine*.2003;10: 34-38.
 10. Kamboj VP. Herbal medicine. *Current science*.2000;78(1):35-51.
 11. Y.W.Chien, Novel Drug Delivery Systems: Transdermal Drug Delivery. *Informa Healthcare* 2003;15(2): 301-380.
 12. Hunt MJ, Barnetson RS. A comparative study of gluconolactone versus benzoyl peroxide in the treatment of acne. *Australas J Dermatol*. 1992;33(3):131–141.
 13. Peck GL, Downing DT, Pandya M, Prolonged remissions of cystic and conglobate acne with 13-cis-retinoic acid. *N Engl J Med*.1979;300(7):329-336.
 14. Bettoli V, Zauli S, Virgili A. Is hormonal treatment still an option in acne today? *Br J Dermatol*. 2015;172 (5):205-220.
 15. Rao GM, Rao CV, Shirwaikar A. Hepatoprotective effects of rubiadin, a major constituent of *Rubia cordifolia* linn. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2006; 103:484–90.
 16. Baldwin HE, Berson DS. Guidelines of care for the management of acne vulgaris. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2016;74(5):945-973.
 17. Alexeyev OA, Morris T, Zouboulis CC, Patrick S. Why we continue to use the name *Propionibacterium acnes*. *Br J Dermatol*. 2018;179(5):12-27.
 18. Sheelu Monga, Pradeep Dhanwal, Ravinder Kumar, Anil Kumar, Vinod Chhokar; Pharmacological and physicochemical properties of Tulsi (*Ocimum gratissimum* L.): An updated review; *The Pharma Innovation Journal*; 2017; 6(4): 181-186.
 19. Loveth Amuche Okeke, Clement Oliseloke Anie, David Chinemerem Nwobodo, Vitus Kasie Okolo; Phytochemical analysis and antibacterial activities of various leaf extracts of *Ocimum gratissimum* and *Newbouldia laevis*; *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Science*. 2023;22(3):144–52.
 20. Ositadinma Chinyer, Okezie Emmanuel, Grace Oka, Chibuike Ibe, Celestine, Victor Chibueze, Miracle Ebubechi, Rachel Oluchukwu; A review on the traditional uses, phytochemistry, and pharmacological activities of clove basil (*Ocimum gratissimum* L.); *Heliyon* ; 2021; 07.
 21. Junaid, Olabode, Onwuliri; The antimicrobial properties of *Ocimum gratissimum* extracts on some selected bacterial gastrointestinal isolates; *African Journal of Biotechnology*; 2006; Vol. 5(22), pp. 2315-2321.
 22. Abayomi M. Ajayi, Solomon Umukoro, Benneth Ben-Azu, Bulus Adzu, Olusegun G. Ademowo; Toxicity and Protective Effect of Phenolic-Enriched Ethylacetate Fraction of *Ocimum gratissimum* (Linn.) Leaf against Acute Inflammation and Oxidative Stress in Rats; *Wiley analytical science journals*; 2017
 23. Unegbu Nnachetam Valentine, Obum-Nnadi Charity Ndidi, Nkwoemeka Ndidi Ethel, Egwuatu Pius Ikenna; Phytochemical and antibacterial activities of *Ocimum gratissimum* on some selected drug resistant bacteria; *Trends in Science & Technology Journal*; 2019; Vol. 4 No. 3 pp. 786 – 789.
 24. Martins AP, Salgueiro LR, Vila R. Composition of the essential oils of *Ocimum canum*, *O. gratissimum* and *O. minimum*. *Planta Med* 1999;65:187–9.
 25. Orafidiya LO, Agbani EO, Oyedele AO, et al. Preliminary clinical tests on topical preparations of *Ocimum gratissimum* Linn leaf essential oil for the treatment of *Acne vulgaris*. *Clin Drug Invest* 2002;22:313–9.
 26. El-Said F, Sofowora EA, Malcolm SA, et al. An investigation into the efficacy of *Ocimum*

- gratissimum as used in Nigerian native medicine. *Planta Med* 1969; 17: 195–20
27. Jedlickova Z, Motti O, Seryi V. Antibacterial properties of the Vietnamese Cajeput oil and Ocimum oil in combination with antibacterial agents. *J Hyg Epidemiol Microbiol Immunol* 1992; 36(3): 303–9
28. Begum J, Yusuf M, Chowdhury U, et al. Studies on essential oils for their antibacterial and antifungal properties. Part 1. Preliminary screening of 35 essential oils. *Bangladesh J Sci Industr Res* 1993; 28(4): 25–34
29. Florence AT, Atwood D, editors. *Physicochemical principles of Pharmacy*. 2nd ed. Basingtoke: Macmillan, 1990: 16–22 Rees JA, Collett JH. A study of drug release from solutions containing surfactants in micellar concentrations. *J Pharm Pharmacol* 1975; 27: 10
30. Evans WC. *Trease and Evans Pharmacognosy*. 15th ed. Edinburgh: Harcourt Publishers Ltd 2002: 255–60
31. Vieira, R.F.; Greyer, R.J.; Paton, A.; Simon, J.E. Genetic diversity of *Ocimum gratissimum* L. based on volatile oil constituents, flavonoids and RAPD markers. *Biochemistry Systematics and Ecology*, Amsterdam, v.29, p.287-304, 2001

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